

Bridgehead Nitrogen Heterocyclic Systems. Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activity of *s*-Triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]thiadiazines, Thiazolo[3,2-*b*]-*s*-triazoles and Isomeric Thiazolo[2,3-*c*]-*s*-triazoles

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The isomeric triazoles (6 and 8) both fused with the 2,3-bond of a thiazole, have been prepared starting from the thiosemicarbazide (2). The triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]thiadiazine (9; R⁶=C₆H₅ and C₆H₄Cl-*p*) arises from the condensation of the triazole (5) with haloketone (R⁶=COCH₂Br). The antibacterial and antifungal activity of the above products have been evaluated.

In continuation of our earlier studies¹ on the regiospecific cyclisation of unsymmetrical mercaptoazoles with bifunctional compounds, we report here the synthesis of some interesting heterocyclic systems derived from unsymmetrical triazoles and the biological activities associated with them.

2-Mercapto-3-β-naphthyl-*s*-triazole (3), derived from the hydrazide (1) through the semicarbazide (2) heated with α-haloketones in anhydrous ethanol under reflux for 3 h gave the uncyclised ketones (4) which underwent PPA cyclisation giving thiazolo[3,2-*b*]-*s*-triazole (6) in exclusion of the thiazolo[2,3-*c*]-*s*-triazole (8) synthesised by an unequivocal method.

which on cyclisation with POCl₃ provided 3-(β-naphthyl)-5-substituted-thiazolo[2,3-*c*]-*s*-triazole (8).

The reaction of 4-amino-5-mercapto-3-(β-naphthyl)-*s*-triazole (5) with α-haloketones under reflux in anhydrous ethanol gave 7-*H*-3-β-naphthyl-6-substituted-*s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]thiadiazines (9) directly in one step. The structures of 6, 8 and 9 were established by elemental analyses and ir and nmr spectral data.

Antimicrobial activity: Compounds 6, 8, 9a and 9b were evaluated for their antimicrobial activity against gram-positive (*Staphylococcus aureus*) and gram-negative (*Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*) bacteria and the fungus (*Candida albicans*) by neat samples and serial plate dilution method².

The MIC value 9b against *P. aeruginosa* and *C. albicans* was found to be 500 μg ml⁻¹. Compounds 6 and 8 were found to be active against *S. aureus* and *C. albicans* when tested as neat samples.

Experimental

Tlc was run on silica-gel plates using acetone-benzene (1 : 3) as irrigant. Melting points are uncorrected. Ir and pmr spectra were recorded on Beckman IR-20 and Perkin-Elmer P-32 (90 MHz) instruments respectively, chemical shifts downfield from TMS.

1-β-Naphthoyl-3-thiosemicarbazide (2): It was prepared by the reaction of β-naphthoylhydrazide (1) with potassium thiocyanate under acidic conditions following the reported method³, (74%), m.p. 205° (Found: N, 16.89; S, 13.37. C₁₂H₁₁N₃OS requires: N, 17.14; S, 13.06%); ν_{max} 755, 820, 870, 1 120, 1 510, 1 610 1 655, 3 250 and 3 300 cm⁻¹.

5-Mercapto-3-(β-naphthyl)-*s*-triazole (3): Compound 2 (8.2 g, 0.033 mol) in 8% NaOH (100 ml) was refluxed for ~3 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled to room temperature and acidified with

(1) R² = H

(2) R² = CSNH₂

(3) R³ = R⁴ = H

(4) R³ = CH₂COR⁵, R⁴ = H

(5) R³ = H, R⁴ = NH₂

(6)

(7)

a, R⁶ = Ph, b, R⁶ = *p*-Cl C₆H₄

(9)

(8)

For (1-9) R¹ = β-Naphthyl

(4-8) R⁵ = *p*-Chlorophenyl

Scheme 1

Condensation of 1-β-naphthoyl-3-thiosemicarbazide (2) with α-haloketones gave 2-(β-naphthoylhydrazino)-4-substituted-thiazole hydrobromide (7)

dilute acetic acid. The solid thus separated was washed with water and crystallised from methanol as colourless needles, m.p. 280° (Found : N, 18.32 ; S, 13.85. C₁₂H₉N₃S requires : N, 18.50 ; S, 14.10%) ; ν_{\max} 760, 810, 850, 880, 1 590, 1 645, 2 600 and 3 100 cm⁻¹.

5-(p-Chlorobenzoylmethylmercapto)-3-(β -naphthyl)-s-triazole (4): A mixture of 3 (2.27 g, 0.01 mol) and *p*-chlorophenacyl bromide (2.34 g, 0.01 mol) in anhydrous ethanol (200 ml) was refluxed for 5 h, then cooled to the room temperature and neutralised with aqueous K₂CO₃. The resulting yellow solid was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol as light yellow crystals (2.4 g, 64%), m.p. 193° (Found : N, 11.51 ; S, 8.83. C₂₀H₁₄N₃OSCl requires : N, 11.07 ; S, 8.43%) ; ν_{\max} 770, 845, 870, 1 520, 1 600, 1 620, 1 690, 3 120 and 3 395 cm⁻¹.

2-(β -Naphthyl)-5-(p-chlorophenyl)thiazolo[3,2-b]-s-triazole (6): A mixture of 4 (1.0 g), P₂O₅ (4 g) and H₃PO₄ (3 ml) was heated in an oil-bath at 150° for about 3 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled, poured into water and neutralised with aqueous K₂CO₃. The resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol as brown granules (0.38 g, 40%), m.p. 185° (Found : C, 65.87 ; H, 3.40 ; N, 11.84 ; S, 9.12. C₂₀H₁₃N₃SCl requires : C, 66.39 ; H, 3.32 ; N, 11.62 ; S, 8.85%) ; ν_{\max} 765, 830, 850, 880, 1 510, 1 615, 3 025 and 3 070 cm⁻¹ ; δ (CDCl₃) 6.97 (1H, s, C₆-H), 7.95 (4H, d, J 9 Hz, *p*-chlorophenyl-H), 7.25–8.35 (5H, m, C-3'-H, C-4'-H, C-5'-H, C-6'-H, C-7'-H), 8.25 (1H, dd, C-8'-H, J_{7',8'} 7.2 Hz *ortho*-coupling, J_{6',8'} 2.7 Hz *meta*-coupling) and 8.65 (1H, s, C-1'-H).

2-(β -Naphthylhydrazino)-4-(p-chlorophenyl)thiazole hydrobromide (7): A mixture of 2 (2.45 g, 0.01 mol) and *p*-chlorophenacyl bromide (2.34 g, 0.01 mol) in anhydrous ethanol (100 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath for 4 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled to room temperature and the solid thus separated was crystallised from ethanol as grey shining crystals (2.8 g, 61%), m.p. 255° (Found : N, 9.23 ; S, 7.28. C₂₀H₁₃N₃OSClBr requires : N, 9.12 ; S, 6.95%) ; ν_{\max} 770, 825, 850, 885, 1 590, 1 585, 1 645, 1 680, 3 100, 3 260 and 3 300 cm⁻¹.

3-(β -Naphthyl)-5-(p-chlorophenyl)thiazolo[2',3-c]-s-triazole (8): A mixture of 7 (1 g) and POCl₃ (10 ml) was heated in an oil-bath at 120–30° for 3 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled, poured into water, neutralised with aqueous K₂CO₃ and the solid thus separated was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol as yellow shining flakes (0.4 g, 51%), m.p. 225° (Found : C, 66.67 ; H, 3.30 ;

N, 11.28 ; S, 9.08. C₂₀H₁₂N₃SCl requires : C, 66.39 ; H, 3.32 ; N, 11.62 ; S, 8.85%) ; ν_{\max} 765, 820, 845, 890 and 1 625 cm⁻¹ ; δ (CDCl₃) 6.97 (1H, s, C-6-H) and 7.17–7.77 (12H, m, ArH).

4-Amino-5-mercapto-3-(β -naphthyl)-s-triazole (5): It was prepared from β -naphthoic acid hydrazide according to the reported method⁴, (84%), m.p. 195° (methanol) (Found : N, 23.40 ; S, 13.56. C₁₂H₁₀N₄S requires : N, 23.14 ; S, 13.22%) ; ν_{\max} 765, 840, 875, 1 515, 1 610, 1 630, 2 620, 3 030, 3 120 and 3 340 cm⁻¹.

7H-3-(β -Naphthyl)-6-phenyl-s-triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazine (9a): A mixture of 5 (2.42 g, 0.01 mol) and phenacyl chloride (1.55 g, 0.01 mol) in anhydrous ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 5 h, then cooled and neutralised with aqueous K₂CO₃. The solid thus separated was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol as light yellow crystals (1.7 g, 50%), m.p. 218° (Found : C, 70.36 ; H, 4.22 ; N, 16.87 ; S, 9.70. C₂₀H₁₄N₄S requires : C, 70.18 ; H, 4.09 ; N, 16.37 ; S, 9.36%) ; ν_{\max} 695, 735, 760, 810, 850, 900, 1 525, 1 585 and 1 620 cm⁻¹ ; δ (CDCl₃+TFA) 4.07 (2H, s, S-CH₂) and 7.37–8.57 (12H, m, ArH). Compound 9b was similarly prepared from 5 and *p*-chlorophenacyl bromide, (58%), m.p. 220° (Found : C, 64.10 ; H, 3.24 ; N, 15.22 ; S, 8.19. C₂₀H₁₃N₄SCl requires : C, 63.74 ; H, 3.35 ; N, 14.87 ; S, 8.50%) ; ν_{\max} 760, 835, 845, 885, 1 500, 1 585 and 1 625 cm⁻¹.

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